

A Correlational Study on Personality Traits and Work Engagement of Teaching and Non-Teaching Personnel

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Abstract. This study investigated the relationship between the Big Five personality traits—Neuroticism, Extraversion, Openness, Agreeableness, and Conscientiousness—and employees' work engagement. It also examined differences in personality traits and engagement when grouped by work classification. Participants included 121 employees from Olivarez College, Tagaytay, consisting of 61 teaching and 60 non-teaching personnel. Findings revealed a significant relationship between all personality traits and levels of work engagement. While personality traits significantly differed between teaching and non-teaching groups, no significant differences were found in their levels of engagement. This indicates that both groups experience similar degrees of energy, dedication, and involvement in their work regardless of role differences. The study concluded that personality traits influence engagement and satisfaction in a higher education setting. Employees who demonstrated cooperation, compassion, and positive interpersonal relationships exhibited higher motivation and engagement. In contrast, individuals with higher neuroticism tended to show lower engagement levels. Additionally, the nature of job roles alone does not determine engagement. The study suggests that school administrators and human resource departments can enhance employee engagement by implementing well-being programs and supportive policies that address both personal and professional needs.

Keywords: Correlational Study; Five Personality Traits; Non-Teaching; Teaching; Work Engagement

Introduction

Academic Institutions are heavily dependent on the capabilities of teaching and non-teaching personnel to fulfill their academic goals and organizational mandates. In previous years, there has been an increase in attention to individual psychological factors, such as personality traits and engagement, that potentially influence employees' attitudes and behaviors, including the ability to cope with stress, manage emotions, and maintain healthy working relationships (Magomedova & Fatima, 2025). Additionally, it could also affect the productivity and performance of the workers, which ultimately affects organizational outcomes (Ansari, 2020). Hence, personality traits and engagement have been linked to the effectiveness of employees to fulfill their roles and responsibilities across different occupational settings.

According to Worthy, Lavigne, and Romero (2026), Personality Traits represent an individual's thought patterns, feelings, and behaviors. The authors also claimed that there are three criteria that define personality traits: consistency, stability, and individual differences. Further, these criteria explain that personality traits must be consistent across interactions, stable over time, and that people have different traits depending on the strength and intensity of the behaviors related to them. McCrae and Costa (1992) introduced five factors that represent the personality traits of an individual: Neuroticism, Extraversion, Openness, Agreeableness, and Conscientiousness. Empirical evidence suggests that these factors can affect performance outcomes at work (Zaidi et al., 2013).

Meanwhile, Employee Engagement refers to the commitment of an employee towards achieving the goals and objectives of the role, and has emerged as one of the important elements in influencing the performance of an organization (Deepalakshmi et al., 2024). Naufer and Kumar (2020) argued that an engaged employee of an organization produces results, does not change jobs frequently, serves as the company's ambassador, and works with passion to achieve organizational goals. Several studies on occupational stress examined how engagement can be improved in the workplace but focused only on identifying its associations

with the work environment and job stressors themselves, not on individual worker factors, including personality (Fuzukaki & Iwata, 2021).

In the Higher Education Sector in the Philippines, several studies have also explored work engagement and its relationship with workload (Maquidato & Bayani, 2024), Performance, and Organizational Support (Negoso, 2021), Leadership (Disilio & Callo, 2024), and Well-being (Abun et al., 2020). While research on the relationship between engagement and work-related personality traits has been limited to how individuals think, act, and feel at work using the Manchester Personality Questionnaire (Lacuesta, Chan, & Bestuer, 2023). With this, the widely accepted Big Five personality traits remain unexplored, creating an empirical gap, particularly among Non-Teaching Personnel who provide back-office support for the success of the Higher Education Institution.

Recognizing this gap, this study aims to examine the relationship between personality traits and work engagement of teaching and non-teaching personnel, to understand how individuals' personality dispositions will influence their level of engagement at work, and to develop a program that will support the productivity and performance of the teaching and non-teaching personnel. The research agenda aligns with the UN Sustainable Development Goals #8, which aims to promote a sustained, inclusive, and productive employment and decent work for all (United Nations, n.d.).

Research Questions

This study aims to investigate the relationship between the personality traits and work engagement of teaching and non-teaching personnel in a higher education institution, and what variables influence these constructs. Hence, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Gender; and
 - 1.3 Work Classification?
2. What are the Levels of Engagement of the Respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1 Vigor;
 - 2.2 Dedication; and
 - 2.3 Absorption?
3. What are the Personality Traits of the Respondents?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' personality traits and employee engagement?
5. Is there a significant difference between the respondents' Personality Traits when grouped according to their work classification?
6. Is there a significant difference between the respondents' levels of Employee Engagement when grouped according to their work classification?

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study focuses on examining the relationship between the Big Five personality traits—Neuroticism, Extraversion, Openness, Agreeableness, and Conscientiousness—and the level of work engagement among teaching and non-teaching personnel in Olivarez College – Tagaytay. Work engagement is specifically measured using the dimensions of vigor, dedication, and absorption. The study includes a total of 121 respondents composed of 61 teaching and 60 non-teaching personnel who meet the inclusion criteria and voluntarily participated in the research. The research is limited to a descriptive-correlational design and relies on self-reported data gathered through standardized instruments, namely the Big Five Aspects Scale (BFAS) and the Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES). The data collection was conducted during the second semester of Academic Year 2025–2026. This study is delimited to one private higher education institution and does not cover other colleges or universities, which limits the generalizability of the findings. It also does not consider other variables that may influence work engagement, such as organizational culture, leadership style, job satisfaction, and external socio-economic factors. Additionally, the study excludes part-time employees and those who do not meet the specified inclusion criteria. The findings are therefore applicable only within the context and conditions under which the data were gathered.

Literature Review

Personality Traits in the Educational Setting

In the Educational setting, personality traits have been found to play an important role in shaping the academic personnel's instructional behaviors, interpersonal relationships with students, and strategies for

coping with challenges (Nuñez & Gula, 2022; Basu & Banerjee, 2024). Adrales et al. (2019) also found that the personality of academic personnel has an impact on the academic performance of the students. Personality traits refer to the consistent patterns of thoughts, feelings, and behaviors that differentiate an individual from others. Among the various models and theories in personality psychology, the Five-Factor Model, which was developed by McCrae & Costa (1992), became one of the most widely accepted theories that identifies an individual's personality traits. The five personality factors are: Openness (O) to experience, which pertains to a trait of an individual to explore something new, and being interested in many topics; Conscientiousness (C) which relates to being organized, hardworking, and often make plans and goals; Extraversion (E) which is the quality of being sociable, assertive, and like to be involved; Agreeableness (A) which is a quality of being kind, caring, and finds positive ways of dealing with problem, and Neuroticism (N) which is generally considered a negative trait as it is characterized by anxiety, tension, and insecurity (Dziak, 2024). McCrae and Costa (1992) suggest that individuals differ in these traits based on their strengths and intensity. Hence, these personality traits can be categorized into positive and negative traits depending on their dispositions in an individual. Positive Personality Traits have a good impact on the work environment, engagement, and employee well-being (Li & Dietrich, 2023). Meanwhile, Negative Personality traits acted as vulnerability factors affecting engagement and performance (Karimi, 2019), such as Neuroticism. Hence, Higher Educational Institutions can ensure that they can deliver quality education to their students by making their Academic personnel effective and efficient by developing their personality traits (Cainday et al., 2023) in a positive manner. Because studies show that academic personnel with a high level of agreeableness and conscientiousness tend to demonstrate higher quality of teaching performance, positive interactions, and higher engagement at work compared to those who scored low. While high levels of neuroticism are linked to low-level performance and disengagement (Basu & Banerjee, 2024), as they report often feeling stressed, unable to handle criticism, and taking things seriously (Gonzales & Rosales, 2022).

Work Engagement in the Academic Profession

Work engagement has emerged as one of the pivotal factors that influence whether the employee remains or leaves the organization (Naufer & Kumar, 2020). According to Zaidi et al. (2013), in recent years, the teaching profession's problems related to academic engagement have received adequate attention due to the high attrition rate of teachers worldwide. The Job Demand Resources-Model explains that environmental factors at work, such as interpersonal interactions, workloads, and leadership styles of supervisors, and personality factors, are responsible for shaping an individual's engagement. Hence, the frequent resignation of educators is due to the complex interaction of the cognitive, emotional, and physical demands of the job and their dominant personality traits. In the Philippine Educational Setting, the primary source of quality education and high academic performance is the academic engagement of its leaders and personnel (Pasco et al., 2025; Maquidato & Bayani, 2024). Meanwhile, to better understand the underlying conditions that could lead to the rise and fall of academic personnel's work engagement, we should explore both personal and environmental influences at work. In the study conducted by Mingoa (2017), educators in Metro Manila identify work-related, financial, and personal factors that affect their teaching engagement. Further, according to Maquidato and Bayani (2024), in Bataan, teachers are resigning due to their excessive workloads, while a steady increase in resignations of teachers in the Davao Region was also seen, with a total of 964 teachers in the last four years leaving their jobs due to administrative workloads and non-teaching responsibilities. Lastly, in the study of Abun et al. (2020) at Ilocos Region, they found that teacher engagement can be positively influenced by equal treatment and respect for teachers' rights, and neglecting these factors can affect the quality of education. Thus, in the educational setting, work engagement can be shaped by multiple factors, which can lead to a rise or fall of teaching quality, student engagement, job satisfaction, and institutional effectiveness. However, the gap still exists in terms of understanding how the concept of work engagement operates in the perception of Non-Teaching personnel.

Methodology

Research Design

The study used the Descriptive-Correlational Research Design to determine the relationship between the level of personality traits and employee engagement of the teaching and non-teaching personnel in Olivarez College – Tagaytay. The descriptive approach was used to properly describe the personality and engagement levels of the participants, while the correlational approach was applied to analyze how the variable corresponds to the other variable (Creswell, 2018). The study will be carried out during the 2nd semester of Academic Year 2025-2026, from March to May 2026, which covers the data gathering and analysis of the results. The single data collection is sufficient for the research, as the independent variable, specifically, the personality traits, is

consistent over time (Worthy, Lavigne, & Romero, 2026; McCrae & Costa, 1992), and concurrent problems in engagement are aimed to be resolved as the situation presents itself.

Sampling Design

To ensure a seamless gathering of data, the researcher used the convenience sampling method. As Golzar, Tajik, and Noor (2022) argued, this was frequently used in both social sciences and educational research, especially when the researcher has access to the population it seeks to study.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Olivarez College – Tagaytay. It is located at Emilio Aguinaldo Highway, Brgy. San Jose, Tagaytay City. The institution accommodates both Filipino and foreign nationalities, who account for approximately 5,000 enrolled students. Meanwhile, its workforce consists of 104 Non-Teaching Personnel who are concerned with performing administrative and operational tasks, and 156 Teaching Personnel with different specializations and courses handled.

Research Participants

To ensure that the survey would produce quality and reliable data for the research, specific inclusion criteria were established for both teaching and non-teaching personnel. For teaching personnel, participants were required to have at least one year of tenure at Olivarez College – Tagaytay, be employed as full-time faculty members, have no pending or administrative cases within the last two semesters, and demonstrate willingness to voluntarily participate in the study. For non-teaching personnel, respondents were required to be regular employees of the institution, possess a minimum of one year tenure, have no part-time employment outside the academic institution, and likewise show voluntary participation. Overall, a total of 120 respondents, who were composed of an equally represented 60 Teaching and 60 Non-Teaching personnel from Olivarez College – Tagaytay, voluntarily participated in the study. The sample size in the study is adequate, considering the inclusion criteria, which exclude the majority of the part-time workers in the Institution. In most studies, at least 30-40 samples can guarantee that using an independent samples t-test produces a reliable result (Singh, 2023; Skaik, 2015). While 121 respondents provide sufficient statistical power and precision for the research with 95% accuracy, and a 90% assurance that it will produce a non-negative result (You, 2012).

Research Instrument

This study utilized a survey questionnaire to collect respondents' demographic data, as well as standardized instruments to measure personality traits and engagement. Personality traits were assessed using the Big Five Aspects Scale (BFAS) developed by DeYoung, Quilty, and Peterson (2007), a 100-item instrument measuring the five major personality domains: openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism. Responses were rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). The BFAS has established construct validity through factor analysis and demonstrates moderate to strong correlations across the Big Five domains, with values ranging from .51 to .64, and stronger correlations with the NEO PI-R scales ranging from .80 to .85. It also shows high reliability and internal consistency, with coefficients ranging from .79 to .90 across domains. In addition, engagement was measured using the Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES), specifically the original 17-item version, where participants rated statements on a 7-point scale from 0 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree). The UWES assesses engagement through three dimensions: vigor, dedication, and absorption, with strong internal consistency values of .84, .89, and .79, respectively. Overall, these instruments are widely validated and appro

Data Gathering Procedure

Before the procedure started, the researcher wrote a letter to the President of Olivarez College – Tagaytay to seek approval to conduct the survey for both Teaching and Non-Teaching Personnel of the Institution and explained its purpose. After securing approval, the researcher started the data gathering by asking the potential respondents if they were willing to participate in the survey, as guided by the inclusion criteria. Personnel who qualified in the established parameters and agreed to participate in the survey were given a profiling sheet and the assessment tools. Informed consent was also included to ensure that they were made aware of the research purpose and as a guarantee that their participation was voluntary. Further, the data gathered from the instruments were tallied and computed based on the assessment procedures and statistical analysis.

Results and Discussions

Research Question 1: What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of Age, Gender, and Work Classification?

Table 1. Frequency Distribution of Participants in terms of Age

Age Range	Count	% of Total
21–30	57	47.11%
31–40	33	27.27%
41–50	17	14.05%
51 and above	14	11.57%
Total	121	100%

The frequency distribution analysis showed that the majority of respondents belonged to the 21–30 age range, comprising 47.11% ($n=57$) of the total sample. Respondents aged 31–40 represented 27.27% ($n=33$), while those within the 41–50 age range accounted for 14.05% ($n=17$). The smallest proportion of respondents belonged to the 51 years old and above category, comprising 11.57% ($n=14$) of the sample. Overall, the findings indicate that the sample was predominantly composed of younger adults, particularly individuals aged 21–30 years, with progressively fewer participants represented in the older age groups.

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of Participants in Terms of Gender

Gender	Count	Percentage
Female	85	70.2 %
Male	36	29.8 %

Table 2 shows that the majority of the respondents were predominantly female ($n = 85$, 70.2%), while male respondents comprised 29.8% of the survey population ($n = 36$).

Table 3. Frequency Distribution of Participants in Terms of Work Classification

Frequencies of Work Classification		
Work Classification	Counts	% of Total
Teaching Personnel	61	50.4 %
Non-Teaching Personnel	60	49.6 %

In terms of Work Classification, Table 3 shows that the respondents were almost equally distributed according to work classification, with 50.4% identified as teaching personnel ($n = 61$) and 49.6% as non-teaching personnel ($n = 60$). This indicates a nearly balanced representation of both groups in the study.

Research Question 2: What are the Levels of Engagement of the Respondents in terms of Vigor, Dedication, and Absorption?

Table 4. Levels of Engagement of the Respondents

Work Engagement	Mean	SD
Vigor	4.72	0.919
Dedication	4.86	0.864
Absorption	4.32	0.834
Total Average of Work Engagement	4.63	0.816

The respondents demonstrated a relatively high level of work engagement, as reflected in the overall mean work engagement score ($M = 4.63$, $SD = 0.816$). Among the dimensions of engagement, Dedication obtained the highest mean score ($M = 4.86$, $SD = 0.864$), suggesting that the respondents generally experienced strong enthusiasm, a sense of significance, and commitment toward their work. Vigor also yielded a high mean score ($M = 4.72$, $SD = 0.919$), indicating that the respondents tended to exhibit energy and resilience in performing their job responsibilities. Meanwhile, Absorption obtained the lowest mean among the three dimensions ($M = 4.32$, $SD = 0.834$), although the score still reflects a favorable level of engagement, implying that respondents were generally immersed and focused on their work activities. Consistent with the previous literature, the result of the present study aligns with how job demands and resources foster employee engagement. For instance, Deligero and Laguador (2014) found that the high levels of engagement of both

teaching and support services personnel in Lyceum of the Philippines University – Batangas were attributed to key resources and demands of the organization, including leadership, communication, rewards and recognition, mission, vision, and values, accountability and responsibility, and corporate social responsibility. This was also supported in the study conducted by Ramos et al. (2021) in a Higher Education Institution in Northern Philippines (Ramos et al., 2021), where Outcomes-based Education implementation, task-ownership, and full support of the academic community sustain work engagement. Moreover, the present study suggests that the respondents possess positive work-related attitudes and psychological involvement in their organization, which may contribute to improved work performance, motivation, and organizational functioning.

Research Question 3: What are the Personality Traits of the Respondents?

Table 5. Personality Traits of the Respondents

Personality Traits	Mean	SD
Neuroticism	2.80	0.296
Agreeableness	3.26	0.166
Conscientiousness	3.42	0.188
Extraversion	3.36	0.245
Openness	3.48	0.225

Table 5 shows the level of personality traits of the participants. The results indicate that the respondents generally exhibited moderate to relatively high levels across the different personality traits. Among the five traits, Openness obtained the highest mean score ($M = 3.48$, $SD = 0.225$), suggesting that the respondents tended to be receptive to new experiences, ideas, and learning opportunities. Conscientiousness also yielded a relatively high mean ($M = 3.42$, $SD = 0.188$), indicating that the respondents were generally organized, responsible, and goal-oriented in their behaviors. Extraversion obtained a mean score of 3.36 ($SD = 0.245$), implying that the respondents moderately demonstrated sociability, enthusiasm, and assertiveness. Agreeableness produced a mean score of 3.26 ($SD = 0.166$), reflecting a tendency among respondents to be cooperative, compassionate, and considerate in interpersonal interactions. Meanwhile, Neuroticism obtained the lowest mean score ($M = 2.80$, $SD = 0.296$), suggesting comparatively lower tendencies toward emotional instability, anxiety, and negative emotional experiences. Overall, the result suggests that the participants of the study demonstrate personality characteristics that are ideal to function properly in their roles and responsibilities, particularly by having a high openness to experience (Nieß & Zacher, 2015). High conscientiousness and low levels of neuroticism (Soto, 2018). Extraversion is also an important personality trait, as workers in the academic field tend to face different people at work every day, requiring them to be more sociable, welcoming, and attentive to the needs of others. This is supported by the study of Soto (2018) that extroverted individuals tend to perform better in social occupations and adapt well in a community. Further, this result implies that the respondents are not only capable of adjusting to the environment of the institution but also likely to maintain a relatively stable behavioral response when facing challenges in their respective roles, specifically, in teaching and administrative functions.

Research Question 4: Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' personality traits and employee engagement?

Table 6. Relationship Between the Respondents' Personality Traits and Employee Engagement

		Neuroticism	Agreeableness	Conscientiousness	Extraversion	Openness
Work Engagement	Pearson's r	-0.313	0.247	0.304	0.342	0.258
	df	119	119	119	119	119
	p-value	< .001	0.006	< .001	< .001	0.004

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to analyze the relationship between the respondents' personality traits and work engagement. Results revealed a significant relationship between all their personality traits and the level of their work engagement. Specifically, a significant negative relationship was found between neuroticism and work engagement ($r(119) = -.313$, $p < .001$), indicating that higher levels of neuroticism were associated with lower levels of employee engagement. This confirms the previous study conducted by Kang and Malvaso (2023), that neuroticism has a negative association with satisfaction and engagement with the job. Meanwhile, agreeableness was significantly and positively correlated with work engagement ($r(119) = .247$, $p = .006$), which suggests that respondents who were more cooperative and

compassionate tended to demonstrate higher engagement. Conscientiousness also showed a significant positive relationship with work engagement ($r(119) = .304, p < .001$), indicating that more organized and responsible individuals were likely to exhibit greater engagement in their work. Similarly, extraversion was significantly positively related to work engagement ($r(119) = .342, p < .001$), which implies that sociable and energetic respondents tended to report higher engagement levels. Openness likewise demonstrated a significant positive relationship with work engagement ($r(119) = .258, p = .004$), suggesting that respondents who were more open to experiences and ideas tended to have higher levels of engagement. Overall, the findings indicate that personality traits are significantly associated with employee engagement among the respondents. The present study strengthens the previous findings, which suggest that personality factors, including conscientiousness, extraversion, neuroticism, and openness to experience, can determine the level of employee engagement and satisfaction (Kang & Malvaso, 2023; Ansari, 2020). Meanwhile, this study contradicts the findings of Ansari (2020), who reported that agreeableness has an insignificant effect on employee engagement. Such a discrepancy can be explained by the nature of the roles of the respondents, as academic work demands more positive social interactions and emotional connectivity with colleagues, parents, and students. Compared to a corporate setting, where engagement is driven by a more structured approach or task-related. Nevertheless, the result of this research suggests that the relationship between personality traits and levels of engagement varies in sample characteristics, occupational roles, and organizational context.

Research Question 5: Is there a significant difference between the respondents' Personality Traits when grouped according to their work classification?

Table 7. The difference between the respondents' Personality Traits when grouped According to their work classification

Personality Traits		Statistic	df	p
Neuroticism	Welch's t	-2.28	118	0.024
Agreeableness	Welch's t	3.73	119	< .001
Conscientiousness	Welch's t	2.74	117	0.007
Extraversion	Welch's t	4.20	114	< .001
Openness	Welch's t	4.04	117	< .001

Note. $H_a \mu$ Teaching Personnel $\neq \mu$ Non-Teaching Personnel

Welch's Independent samples t-test was used to analyze the difference in the personality traits between teaching and non-teaching personnel. The results revealed significant differences in the respondents' personality traits when grouped according to work classification. Specifically, Neuroticism showed a statistically significant difference between teaching and non-teaching personnel ($t(118) = -2.28, p = .024$), with a small effect size, $d = -0.415$, indicating that one group exhibited lower levels of neuroticism than the other. It also indicates that the two groups differed in terms of emotional instability and negative emotional tendencies. Similarly, agreeableness significantly differed between the groups ($t(119) = 3.73, p < .001$), with a moderate effect size, $d = 0.679$, suggesting meaningful variation in interpersonal tendencies between the groups. The results in this personality trait also suggest variations in cooperativeness, compassion, and interpersonal tendencies between teaching and non-teaching personnel. Conscientiousness also demonstrated a significant difference ($t(117) = 2.74, p = .007$), implying that the groups varied in organization, responsibility, and goal-directed behaviors with a moderate effect size, $d = 0.498$, indicating differences in organization and responsibility. Moreover, a significant difference was found in extraversion ($t(114) = 4.20, p < .001$, indicating differences in sociability, enthusiasm, and assertiveness between the two work classifications with a moderate effect size, $d = 0.762$, suggesting substantial variation in sociability and energy levels across groups. Lastly, Openness likewise significantly differed between teaching and non-teaching personnel ($t(117) = 4.04, p < .001$ with a large effect size, $d = 0.734$, indicating meaningful differences in openness to experience between teaching and non-teaching personnel. These results propose variations in openness to experiences, creativity, and intellectual curiosity. Overall, the findings indicate that work classification is significantly associated with differences in personality traits among the respondents. This is supported by the study that the big five personality factors and their differences in every individual play a crucial role in determining their performance in their respective work assignments (Eshete et al., 2025). This also validates the assumption of Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Theory, that personality traits are antecedents of job demands and job resources, and their capability of being adjusted as the situation presents itself, "can act as mediators between job characteristics and employee engagement" (Schaufeli, 2017).

Research Question 6: Is there a significant difference between the respondents' levels of Employee Engagement when grouped according to their work classification?

Table 8. Difference between the respondents' levels of Employee Engagement when grouped according to their work classification

Work Engagement (W.E.)		Statistic	df	p		Effect Size
Vigor	Welch's t	0.174	115	0.862	Cohen's d	0.0316
Dedication	Welch's t	0.854	113	0.395	Cohen's d	0.1554
Absorption	Welch's t	0.729	107	0.468	Cohen's d	0.1326
WE Total Average	Welch's t	0.615	112	0.540	Cohen's d	0.1120

Note. H_a μ Teaching Personnel \neq μ Non-Teaching Personnel

Welch's Independent samples t-test was used to analyze the difference in the level of work engagement between teaching and non-teaching personnel. The results revealed that there were no significant differences in employee engagement between teaching and non-teaching personnel across all dimensions. For Vigor, the difference between groups was not statistically significant ($t(115) = 0.174, p = .862$), with a negligible effect size, $d = 0.032$, indicating virtually no meaningful difference in energy and mental resilience at work. Similarly, Dedication showed no significant difference between the groups ($t(113) = 0.854, p = .395$), with a small effect size, $d = 0.155$, suggesting comparable levels of enthusiasm, pride, and sense of significance in work. Absorption also did not differ significantly ($t(107) = 0.729, p = .468$), with a small effect size, $d = 0.133$, indicating similar levels of concentration and immersion in work tasks across groups. Finally, the total average of the respondents' work engagement likewise showed no significant difference between teaching and non-teaching personnel ($t(112) = 0.615, p = .540$), with a negligible effect size, $d = 0.112$, suggesting that overall employee engagement is comparable between the two groups. Overall, the findings indicate that work classification is not associated with significant differences in employee engagement, which validates the findings of Deligero and Laguador (2014) that both teaching and non-teaching personnel experience similar levels of energy, commitment, and involvement in their work, despite the differences in their job roles and responsibilities, regardless of whether it is high or low. The result also implies that both work classifications experience a similar level of demands at work and access to resources. This supports the assumption of the Job Demands-Resources model that engagement is shaped by a balanced approach between needs and resources at work, rather than the classification of tasks being performed.

Ethical Considerations

Before the study was conducted, the researcher sought approval from the authors of the assessment test used in this study to ensure the responsible use of the tools and appropriate resources would be provided by the authors to help in interpreting the data collected. The researcher also sought permission from the Management of Olivarez College – Tagaytay to ensure that the research would not violate any research policy of the Institution. The names of the participants were also not mandatorily collected to ensure their anonymity. Further, when the data is no longer needed, it will be disposed of in accordance with the provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Conclusion

This research concludes that Olivarez College – Tagaytay has a conducive working environment for teaching and non-teaching roles, as both working groups demonstrated a high level of employee engagement. They also generally exhibited moderate to high levels of positive personality traits across the big five personality domains, suggesting that they tended to be receptive to new experiences, ideas, and learning opportunities; generally organized, responsible, and goal-oriented; sociable, enthusiastic, and assertive; and cooperative, compassionate, and considerate in interpersonal interactions. While at the same time, less likely to experience negative emotions and stress. Moreover, the current research proves that in the context of a higher education institution, personality traits can influence the level of engagement and satisfaction of an employee. For instance, those who were more cooperative, compassionate, and able to maintain a significant positive relationship at work tended to demonstrate higher enthusiasm, a sense of significance, and commitment toward their work; exhibit energy and resilience in performing their job responsibilities; and focus on their daily activities. On the other hand, higher levels of neuroticism were associated with lower levels of employee engagement. The findings of this research also revealed that personality traits are antecedents of job demands and job resources, and their capability to be adjusted as the situation presents itself can act as mediators between job characteristics and employee engagement. Lastly, the result of the study also implies

that in the context of higher education institutions, work engagement is not necessarily determined by the nature of the roles and responsibilities of the academic personnel.

Reccomendations

Based on the findings of the study, several comprehensive recommendations are proposed for academic institutions, human resource units, personnel, and future researchers. At the institutional level, school administrators are encouraged to develop and implement structured policies that promote psychological safety, aligned with Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 8, ensuring inclusive, respectful, and supportive learning and working environments for all stakeholders, including students, faculty, and parents. Such policies should clearly define acceptable conduct, establish mechanisms for risk-free expression, and enforce anti-discrimination and anti-bullying measures to enhance engagement and institutional productivity. In addition, the implementation of an employee well-being policy is strongly recommended to support both teaching and non-teaching personnel, emphasizing workload balance, mental health promotion, and structured initiatives such as self-care periods in compliance with occupational safety and health standards. At the human resource level, it is recommended to introduce evidence-based stress management programs and employee support groups to mitigate the negative effects of stress-related traits, particularly neuroticism, while leveraging positive traits such as agreeableness and extraversion to strengthen workplace relationships and collaboration. Furthermore, recruitment and selection processes should integrate personality-based alignment strategies to ensure that individual traits correspond effectively with job roles, thereby enhancing performance and job satisfaction. For teaching and non-teaching personnel, continuous professional development through training, workshops, and academic engagement is encouraged to foster adaptability and innovation, while the adoption of emotion regulation strategies is essential in managing occupational stress and sustaining work engagement. Finally, future researchers are advised to extend this line of inquiry by employing mixed-methods or longitudinal research designs, incorporating larger and more diverse samples across multiple institutions to improve generalizability, and exploring additional variables that may further explain the complex relationship between personality traits and work engagement in academic settings.

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